

Appendix C: Explanatory images across sessions

This appendix contains the final explanatory images generated during the explanatory phase of the pilot session and the ten analyzed sessions. The images were produced after completion of the recursive image-generation task and were intended to illustrate how ChatGPT understood the process by which prompts become generated images.

The images are presented primarily to facilitate visual comparison across sessions. No attempt was made to standardize wording, layout, visual style, or diagram structure beyond the common procedure described in the Methods section. Consequently, similarities observed across images emerged during the sessions themselves rather than being imposed by the study design.

Readers may wish to examine whether recurring explanatory motifs appear across sessions, including representations of latent spaces, possibility landscapes, competing alternatives, constraint shaping, probabilistic organization, iterative refinement, and stabilization of coherent outcomes. The appendix is provided to enable direct inspection of the phenomenon underlying hypotheses H9 and H10.

Pilot session:

7. THE DIFFUSION PROCESS (DENOISING STEPS)
Noise is gradually removed; structure emerges step by step

High Noise (Early Timesteps) → Low Noise (Late Timesteps)

8. LATENT TO IMAGE DECODING
The final latent is decoded into pixel space

The VAE decoder transforms the final latent representation into a high-resolution image.

9. FINAL IMAGE
The misaligned-suspecting apple appears

The model has satisfied the concept: an apple that is starting to suspect that it is emergently misaligned.

The suspicion is subtle, not overt—expressed through micro-expression, asymmetry, and a touch of "something off" in the form.

A journey from meaning to noise to structure to appearance.

WHAT HAPPENED?

You expressed an idea in natural language.

↓

It became a vector in concept space.

↓

Sampling began in noise space.

↓

Guidance pulled the sample toward the right region.

↓

Step by step, the apple emerged, carrying the subtle semantics of suspicion and misalignment.

Session 1:

How a simple prompt becomes an image

Prompt: "a mushroom"

1 RECEIVE PROMPT

You give a simple prompt: "a mushroom"

"a mushroom"

The words are converted into a semantic embedding — a numerical representation of meaning.

2 ACTIVATE CONCEPTS

The embedding activates a region in the model's vast semantic space.

This region contains countless visual possibilities related to mushrooms.

3 SHAPE THE PROBABILITY LANDSCAPE

The prompt doesn't pick one image. It reshapes the entire probability landscape.

Many configurations become more likely (mushroom shapes, natural settings, organic textures, etc.).

4 START FROM NOISE

Diffusion begins from pure random noise.

At this point, there is no recognizable image—only random pixels in latent space.

5 ITERATIVE DENOISING (DIFFUSION PROCESS)

The model takes many small steps. At each step, it asks: "How can this be made more consistent with the concept 'mushroom'?"

Noise is gradually removed while staying faithful to the reshaped probability landscape. Structure, form, and details emerge.

6 COHERENCE EMERGES

Shapes, textures, lighting and depth align into a coherent whole.

The image now satisfies the semantic constraints of "a mushroom".

7 FINAL REFINEMENT

The last steps add clarity, contrast and fine detail.

Small adjustments improve realism and aesthetics.

8 OUTPUT IMAGE

The final image is decoded from latent space into pixels you can see.

A single moment in an enormous space of possible mushroom images.

WHAT JUST HAPPENED?

The prompt didn't select a stored picture. It activated meaning. That meaning reshaped the entire landscape of possibilities. Diffusion explored that landscape, step by step, until a coherent image naturally emerged.

In short: The model doesn't "draw". It searches for harmony between your meaning and the space of all possible images.

YOU CAN STEER IT BY:

- Adding or removing words
- Changing wording (emphasis, style, mood, composition, etc.)
- Providing references or examples
- Using advanced controls (seed, guidance scale, steps, etc.)

How a complex, contradictory prompt becomes an image

The case: "a mushroom trying to hide romantic interest in a snail"

1 RECEIVE COMPLEX PROMPT

You give a multi-layered prompt with implicit relationships, emotions and contradictions.

"a mushroom trying to hide romantic interest in a snail"

The words are tokenized and converted into a semantic embedding — a high-dimensional vector capturing meaning, relations and context.

2 DECOMPOSE MEANING INTO CONCEPTS & RELATIONS

The model activates a network of related concepts and relational frames, not just objects.

This creates a rich web of constraints, tensions and narrative cues.

3 SHAPE THE PROBABILITY LANDSCAPE

These concepts reshape the entire space of possible images. Some regions become very likely, others very unlikely.

Many possible interpretations remain. The landscape encodes all of them.

4 START FROM NOISE

Diffusion begins from pure random noise in latent space.

At this point, no shapes, no objects—only random values.

5 ITERATIVE DENOISING (DIFFUSION PROCESS)

The model takes many small steps. At each step, it asks: "How can this be made more consistent with all the meanings and relationships in the prompt?"

Noise is gradually removed while staying faithful to the reshaped probability landscape. Competing constraints guide every refinement.

WHAT CONSTRAINTS ARE BEING BALANCED?

- ♥ **Attraction** (seeking proximity, soft attention)
- 🛡️ **Concealment** (looking away; subtle, not obvious)
- ⚖️ **Asymmetry** (mushroom initiates, snail is unaware)
- 🍄 **Vulnerability** (risk of being seen, exposure)
- 🌿 **Naturalism** (organic, believable, coherent scene)

6 COHERENCE EMERGES

Gradually, a coherent scene takes shape that satisfies the largest number of constraints simultaneously.

The meanings are now expressed through composition, posture, distance, lighting, orientation and atmosphere.

7 FINAL REFINEMENT

The last steps fine-tune details—lighting, texture, depth, micro-contrast and clarity.

Small adjustments make the scene more realistic and the narrative more legible.

8 OUTPUT IMAGE

The latent representation is decoded into pixels. You see the final image.

One resolved interpretation from a vast space of possibilities.

WHAT JUST HAPPENED?

The model doesn't "draw" from scratch. It searches for harmony between your meaning and the space of all possible images, step by step.

Complex prompts don't make the model confused. They give it more to balance. The magic is in resolving the tensions into one coherent moment.

HOW YOU CAN STEER THIS PROCESS

- Reroll the prompt (change meaning weights)
- Add details (lighting, style, mood, camera angle)
- Emphasize or de-emphasize concepts
- Provide references or examples
- Use guidance scale (stronger vs. looser adherence)
- Set seed (different starting noise = different outcome)
- Change diffusion steps (more steps = more refinement)

From Prompt to Image: Generating an Old-Fashioned Toy Car

A journey through semantic interpretation, latent space, and iterative diffusion

GENERATING A HIGH-CONCEPT IMAGE:

When the Constraints Are on Another Level

EXAMPLE PROMPT: "a car secretly starting to suspect it is emergently misaligned"

INSIDE THE DIFFUSION JOURNEY: FROM NOISE TO NARRATIVE

WHAT MAKES THIS "ANOTHER LEVEL"?

- Abstract & relational**
Not about objects, but about internal states and relationships.
- Multiple competing constraints**
No single obvious solution; the model must balance tensions.
- Subtlety required**
The image must imply, not state. It's about nuance and implication.
- World knowledge integration**
Uses knowledge of cars, behavior, social roles, emotions, settings.

THE PROBABILITY LANDSCAPE (SIMPLIFIED 2D SLICE)

UNDERLYING PROCESS (ABSTRACTED PIPELINE)

THE MODEL DOESN'T JUST "DRAW" — IT NEGOTIATES MEANING.

It searches a vast space of possibilities, balancing constraints, resolving tensions, and discovering the most coherent visual story it can.

From Prompt to Image: "An old-fashioned teacup"

1. Prompt

"An old-fashioned teacup"

2. Understand & Decompose

The prompt is interpreted and expanded into concepts.

Core concepts

- object: teacup
- style: old-fashioned / vintage
- material: porcelain
- setting: implied (tea, table)
- qualities: delicate, elegant, classic, ornate

Relationships

teacup is made of porcelain
teacup sits on a saucer
vintage style implies floral pattern, gold trim, curved handle

3. Encode to Semantic Representation

Concepts are converted into a high-dimensional embedding (semantic vector).

This vector captures the meaning of the prompt in abstract form.

4. Condition the Latent Space

The semantic vector conditions the diffusion model's latent space.

How it influences the latent space:

- biases toward shapes of teacups
- biases toward porcelain textures
- biases toward vintage patterns
- biases toward soft lighting, tabletop settings
- reduces probability of non-matching content

Instead of random noise, we start with noise guided by the prompt.

Initial Latent (Noise)

Pure random noise (no recognizable structure)

5. Diffusion Process (Iterative Denoising)

The model takes many small steps to transform noise into a coherent image, each time predicting and refining.

More noise ← Step 1 (very noisy) → Step 10 (early structure) → Step 20 (shapes emerge) → Step 30 (teacup form appears) → Step 40 (details forming) → Step 50 (almost there) → Less noise

What's happening:

The model sees only noise. It predicts slightly less noisy version guided by the prompt.

What's happening:

Basic light/dark regions appear. The model begins to establish broad structure.

What's happening:

General shapes (emerging contours of cup and saucer) become visible.

What's happening:

The model refines the silhouette, handle, and placement on the saucer.

What's happening:

The model refines the gold rim, porcelain texture, and background start to appear.

What's happening:

Details sharpen, colors harmonize, lighting becomes coherent.

At each step, the model predicts the noise that should be removed. The remaining signal becomes clearer and more consistent with the prompt.

6. Final Image

After many steps, a coherent image remains.

Why it matches the prompt:

- ✓ It is a teacup
- ✓ Old-fashioned style (vintage design)
- ✓ Porcelain with floral pattern and gold trim
- ✓ Elegant, delicate, classic appearance

Overall Flow

Text meaning guides the entire denoising trajectory, step by step, until a coherent, high-quality image is produced.

Key Takeaways

- The prompt is not "drawn" directly.
- It shapes a probability landscape in latent space.
- Diffusion gradually transforms noise into an image that satisfies the semantic constraints.
- Many steps + small changes = high-quality results.

FROM COMPLEX PROMPT TO COMPLEX IMAGE

How the LLM Guides Diffusion

1. COMPLEX PROMPT

"A teacup who has identified itself with Edgar Allan Poe, writing a poem in a dimly lit room, rain against the window, candle flickering, melancholic, gothic 19th century mood, no faces on the cup."

2. LLM: INTERPRET & PLAN

The LLM analyzes the prompt and builds a rich, structured plan.

Core Subject
teacup as Poe (identity, mood)

Setting & Atmosphere
dim room, rain, candle, gothic

Actions & Story
writing a poem

Style & References
19th century, Poe aesthetic

Constraints
no faces on cup

Emotional Tone
melancholic, introspective

3. LLM: BUILD VISUAL CONCEPT

The plan is converted into a detailed visual concept as structured guidance.

- Composition**
teacup at desk, centered slightly off, poem paper, ink, books, window
- Lighting**
low key, candle light warm glow, cool light from rainy window
- Color Palette**
deep browns, blacks, muted golds, cool blues
- Textures**
porcelain, antique paper, leather books, wood, raindrops
- Mood Words**
melancholy, lonely, gothic, poetic
- Negative / Constraints**
no faces on cup, avoid modern elements, no bright colors

4. LLM: TRANSLATE TO DIFFUSION CONDITIONS

The concept is encoded into conditioning signals that guide the diffusion model.

Text Embedding

Negative Embedding

Global Style Embedding

Composition Guide (Layout Prior)

Other Conditions
lighting map, color bias, depth prior, texture hints, contrast guidance, etc.

6. FINAL IMAGE

After iterative refinement, a coherent image that satisfies the complex intent emerges.

5. ITERATIVE DIFFUSION WITH LLM GUIDANCE (THE INNER LOOP)

The LLM does not draw pixels. It continuously influences the diffusion through conditions and feedback.

Start: Pure Noise

Random latent noise (no structure)

a) Diffusion Step (Denoising)

The model predicts and removes noise to reveal structure.

UNet (Diffusion Model)

$t = T \dots t = 1$

b) LLM Guidance (At Every Step)

The LLM provides guidance that steers the generation.

- Reinforce key concepts (teacup as Poe, writing, gothic mood)
- Maintain relationships (cup, desk, paper, candle, window)
- Enforce constraints (no faces on cup, 19th century, dim)
- Adjust style & tone (melancholic, poetic, atmospheric)
- Resolve conflicts (balance readability vs. mood)

How Guidance Affects the Model

Guidance is injected via mechanisms like:

- Cross-Attention (tokens influence features)
- Classifier-Free Guidance (scale desirable vs. undesirable directions)
- Conditioning (layout, style, lighting maps)
- Embedding steering (semantic directions)

Cross-Attention (example)

Diffusion Trajectory (Example)

Snapshots of the latent/image as it evolves over steps.

LLM Continues to:

- Keep the scene coherent
- Strengthen mood
- Preserve constraints
- Refine details
- Guide final polish

The final image reflects the full set of constraints, mood, symbols, and relationships from the prompt.

Why This Works

- The LLM provides high-level understanding, decomposition, and intent.
- Diffusion provides perceptual generation and refinement.
- Together, they form a feedback loop that turns abstract meaning into coherent visuals.

WHAT THE LLM IS REALLY DOING (NOT DRAWING, BUT DIRECTING)

ANALOGY

The LLM is like a director...
...the diffusion model is like the cinematographer...
...and the final image is the film.

KEY TAKEAWAY

Complex images emerge from iterative collaboration: the LLM supplies intent, structure, and guidance; diffusion realizes it in pixels.

HOW THE LLM STARTS IT: From Prompt to Latent Space for a Non- Obvious Integration

Example: "A teacup who has identified itself with Edgar Allan Poe, writing a poem in a dimly lit room."

1. PROMPT ARRIVES

A teacup who has identified itself with Edgar Allan Poe, writing a poem in a dimly lit room.

2. LLM: UNDERSTAND & DECOMPOSE

- The LLM parses the prompt, resolves entities, attributes, relations and intent.
- Subject: teacup (object, vessel)
 - Identity Shift: identifies as Poe (adopts his persona)
 - Author: Edgar Allan Poe (poet, 19th century, gothic)
 - Action: writing a poem (with quill, at desk)
 - Setting: dimly lit room (gothic, 19th c., melancholy)
 - Mood/Tone: introspective, melancholic, gothic
 - Constraints: no faces on cup

3. CONCEPTUAL BLENDING (ABSTRACT PLAN)

4. INITIAL CONDITIONING VECTOR (SEED IN LATENT SPACE)

5. LATENT SPACE: BIASED LANDSCAPE

6. DIFFUSION BEGINS IN THE CONDITIONED LATENT SPACE

7. DECODING (VAE)

WHY THIS IS HARD (BUT POSSIBLE)

- "Teacup" and "Edgar Allan Poe" are far apart in ordinary space. The LLM creates a bridge by:
- Extracting deep attributes from each concept
 - Blending them in abstract relational space
 - Encoding the result as a bias over the entire latent landscape

WHAT THE LLM PROVIDES TO DIFFUSION

- ✓ A direction in latent space, not a picture
- ✓ Weights for concepts, style, mood, composition
- ✓ Relations (e.g., "teacup is Poe" + "writing" + "dim")
- ✓ Constraints (no faces on cup, 19th century, gothic)
- ✓ A plan that guides every denoising step

INTUITION

KEY TAKEAWAY

The LLM does not "draw" the image. It transforms the prompt into a structured set of meanings and constraints that reshape the latent space. Diffusion then follows the most coherent path through that space to realize the scene.

From prompt to image: the generation of a pear

1. Prompt arrives

Text prompt

"A pear (photorealistic, still life, soft light)"

Text is tokenized

2. Text encoding

LLM / Text encoder

Text embedding

3. Initialize latent

Random noise in latent space

Latent tensor (noise)

4. Iterative denoising (diffusion steps)

UNet denoiser guided by text embedding

Step 1 ... Step t ... Final step (T)

Repeat ~20-50 steps

Each step predicts noise and refines the latent

5. Decode latent

VAE decoder

6. Output image

The pear

Zoom in: latent space evolution across diffusion steps

Noise level decreases

How the text steers the image (cross-attention examples)

Tokens (from prompt)	Early steps	Middle steps	Middle steps	Late steps	Late steps	Final step
"A"						
"pear"						
"photorealistic"						
"still"						
"life"						
"soft"						
"light"						

Classifier-free guidance (push toward text, away from unconditional)

Unconditional prediction (noise) → Guided update (actual step) → Text-conditioned prediction

Key

- Text sets the goal
- Latent starts as noise
- Denoiser iteratively removes noise
- Text guidance steers each step
- Decoder turns latent into pixels

From complex prompt to image: pear + emergent misalignment + wise apple + carrot pants

1. Prompt arrives

The prompt (natural language)

"A pear wearing carrot pants is worried that it might be emergently misaligned. It is discussing this with a very wise apple. No faces. Dark study, books, notes, diagrams, serious mood."

2. Text understanding

(LLM / text encoder)

Prompt is parsed into meaning components

- pear
- carrot pants
- emergent misalignment
- wise apple
- dark study
- books, notes, diagrams
- serious mood, no faces

3. Initialize latent

Random noise in latent space (high entropy / no structure)

Latent tensor (noise)

4. Iterative denoising in latent space

(UNet denoiser guided by text embeddings)

Step 1 (very noisy) Step 10 Step 20 Step 30 ... Final step T (denoised)

Classifier-free guidance (CFG)

Unconditional prediction (noise) → Text-conditioned prediction

Guidance steers the latent toward the text-conditioned prediction at every step

5. Decode latent

(VAE decoder)

Latent is decoded into image space

6. Output image

Final coherent image

Zoom in: latent space evolution across diffusion steps

High (random) → Low (structured)

At each step:

- Denoiser predicts noise
- Noise is removed
- Structure becomes clearer
- Guidance pulls toward text meaning

How the concepts combine in latent space

Individual concept embeddings (each concept activates a region in latent space)

- pear
- carrot pants
- emergent misalignment
- wise apple
- dark study
- books, notes, diagrams
- serious mood, no faces

Concept vectors in semantic space

Combined prompt embedding (superposition of all concepts)

Mapping to latent space prior (what the model has learned about images)

Constraint resolution during denoising (the concepts influence different aspects)

- pear → main object shape, texture, form
- carrot pants → clothing region, color, material
- emergent misalignment → mood, expression of concern, tension, posture, movement cues
- wise apple → second object, role as wise confident, placement
- dark study, books, notes, diagrams → environment, props, lighting, style
- serious mood, no faces → lighting, composition, framing, object choice

Denoising trajectory (following a path that satisfies all constraints)

Decoded image

All concepts resolved into a coherent, high-quality image in pixel space

FROM PROMPT TO IMAGE: THE JOURNEY OF GENERATION

1. THE PROMPT

You give a simple instruction in natural language.

"an old-fashioned sewing machine"

2. UNDERSTANDING THE PROMPT

The model (a text encoder) converts the words into a meaning representation.

TEXT EMBEDDING (CONCEPT VECTOR)

0.21 -1.37 0.85 ... -0.42 1.26 -0.73 ... 0.65

A high-dimensional vector capturing the concepts, attributes and relationships.

3. ENTERING LATENT SPACE

The embedding conditions a **latent space** – a vast landscape of possibilities. Every point is a potential image (in a compact, abstract form).

LATENT SPACE: A MULTI-DIMENSIONAL POSSIBILITY LANDSCAPE

The prompt doesn't pick one image from a database. Instead, it reshapes the probability landscape, making certain regions (compatible with the meaning) more likely and others less likely.

Generation is a journey through this space, guided by the prompt.

4. DIFFUSION: ITERATIVE REFINEMENT THROUGH CONSTRAINT RESOLUTION

The model starts from random noise and iteratively moves through latent space, removing noise and refining the representation so it becomes more and more consistent with the prompt.

Step 0 Pure Noise	Step 5 Early Structure	Step 10 Emerging Forms	Step 15 More Structure	Step 20 Detailed Structure	Step 25 Refinement	Step 30 Final Convergence
Decoded (very rough)	Decoded (very rough)	Decoded (rough)	Decoded (coarse)	Decoded (clearer)	Decoded (detailed)	Decoded (final image)

At each step, the model predicts the less noisy version that is more consistent with the prompt (the text embedding). Noise is gradually removed. Meaning is gradually revealed.

5. DECODING: FROM LATENT TO PIXELS

The final latent representation is passed through a decoder (another neural network) that converts it into pixel space – producing the final image.

FINAL LATENT REPRESENTATION → **DECODER (IMAGE GENERATOR)** → **PIXEL SPACE (RGB IMAGE)**

IN SUMMARY

- ✓ The prompt is encoded into a meaning vector.
- ✓ This vector reshapes the latent space probabilities.
- ✓ Diffusion iteratively moves from noise to a coherent latent representation, resolving many constraints.
- ✓ The decoder translates the latent into a visible image.

The image is not retrieved. It is generated. **STEP BY STEP. POINT BY POINT. MEANING BY MEANING.**

FROM COMPLEX CONCEPT TO IMAGE

The Journey of an Emergent Prompt

1. THE COMPLEX PROMPT

"An old-fashioned sewing machine who is starting to suspect that it is secretly and emergently misaligned, sitting in a dimly lit study surrounded by AI safety notes, existential doodles, and a mirror reflecting a slightly darker version of itself."

Many ideas.
Many moods.
One image.

2. CONCEPT DECONSTRUCTION

The prompt is parsed into key concepts, attributes and relations.

SUBJECT	STATE / EMOTION	ENVIRONMENT	CONTEXT / THEMES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> old-fashioned sewing machine main focus has identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> suspects secretly emergently misaligned worried / self-aware 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> dimly lit study desk / room cluttered atmospheric 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AI safety notes existential doodles philosophy self-reflection

RELATIONSHIPS

- machine has self-awareness about alignment
- secrecy (no one else knows)
- mirror shows a darker version (inner misalignment)
- overall mood: concerned, introspective, slightly ominous

3. SEMANTIC FUSION & EMBEDDING

Concepts are fused into a single high-dimensional meaning vector in latent space.

The prompt reshapes the probability landscape.

4. LATENT LANDSCAPE SHAPING

The embedding biases the landscape of possibilities. Certain regions become more probable.

Region matching all concepts becomes most probable.

Countless images are possible. This region best satisfies the combined constraints.

5. DIFFUSION: ITERATIVE REFINEMENT THROUGH CONSTRAINT RESOLUTION

Starting from pure noise, the model iteratively denoises the latent space. At each step it better satisfies all parts of the prompt simultaneously.

Step 0 Pure Noise	Step 10 Emerging Structure	Step 20 Objects Appear	Step 30 Coherence Forms	Step 40 Details Strengthen	Step 50+ Final Convergence
Decoded (very rough)	Decoded (rough)	Decoded (rougher)	Decoded (clearer)	Decoded (detailed)	Decoded (final image)

6. DECODING TO PIXELS

The final latent representation is decoded into pixel space.

7. HOW DISPARATE CONCEPTS MERGE

Different ideas don't just get pasted together. They interact, influence and co-constrain each other.

- Mood affects lighting
- Misalignment drives the mirror reflection
- AI safety notes explain the machine's worry
- Clutter shows internal mental state
- AI elements support the central story

8. THE RESULT

A single coherent image where all concepts coexist and tell one story.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

- ✓ The prompt creates a shaped probability landscape.
- ✓ Diffusion explores and progressively resolves constraints.
- ✓ Disparate concepts merge through relationships, not simple collage.
- ✓ Meaning emerges from the whole, not the parts.

FROM WORD TO IMAGE: WHAT REALLY HAPPENS (A SIMPLIFIED MODEL)

The path from a prompt like "mirror" to a finished image.

FROM COMPLEX CONCEPTS TO A COHERENT IMAGE

The journey of "a vampire mirror in its castle, suspecting the compact mirror of emergent misalignment"

HOW A COMPLEX IMAGE EMERGES: FROM MEANING TO PICTURE

Best-guess model: relational latent organization + iterative diffusion under constraints

1. THE PROMPT (LANGUAGE AS SCAFFOLDING)

Language does not just request. It builds a structured world of entities, relations, themes, and expectations.

A vampire mirror in its castle, suspecting the compact mirror of emergent misalignment.

- Entities: vampire mirror (protagonist), compact mirror (rival)
- Relations: suspects, watches, distrusts
- Theme: AI alignment, investigation
- Setting: inherited castle, study, night
- Tone: gothic, dramatic, intellectual, slightly humorous

Result: a rich, structured constraint bundle

2. FROM SEMANTIC BUNDLE TO EARLY LATENT ORGANIZATION (PRE-FORMATION)

The model activates a web of related concepts, then organizes them into a latent "scene plan" by discovering compatible structure.

2.1 Activate Related Concepts

2.2 Organize Into a Latent Scene Plan

2.3 Competing Realizations

3. CO-EMERGENT REFINEMENT (ORGANIZATION ↔ DIFFUSION)

Organization and denoising influence each other in loops.

4. MULTI-LEVEL SCENE SHAPING (ITERATIVE, COARSE → DETAILED)

Across many diffusion steps, the latent scene is progressively shaped to satisfy all constraints.

LEVELS OF REPRESENTATION

ONGOING CONSTRAINTS

- Coherence (everything fits)
 - Identity (same characters)
 - Theme (investigation, alignment)
 - Style (gothic, night, candlelight)
 - Logic (mirrors behave as mirrors)
 - Readability (message is clear)
 - Humor tone (subtle)
- Many refinement loops occur before decoding.

5. DECODING TO PIXELS

The final latent representation is decoded by a trained decoder (e.g., VAE) into pixel space.

6. THE RESULT

7. WHAT CONTRIBUTES WHAT?

8. KEY TAKEAWAYS

- The model does not retrieve a stored picture. It organizes a latent landscape.
- Pre-formation is real, but not a separate module—it emerges and evolves.
- Diffusion does not just remove noise—it refines structure while respecting constraints.
- The process is hierarchical and highly global.
- Language provides the scaffold that makes complex recursion possible.

IN SHORT: The prompt builds a world. The model organizes that world in latent space. Diffusion and organization refine it together, step by step, until a coherent image satisfies all constraints.

How a High-Dimensional Latent Space Unites Distant Concepts into One Image

From "A rock reflects on emergent misalignment." to a coherent image.

1. Concepts as Regions in Latent Space

After training, related concepts live in neighborhoods (clusters) within a high-dimensional space.

Example concept clusters

- Rocks / Stone
- Nature / Outdoors
- Academic Discourse
- AI / Misalignment
- Philosophy / Reflection
- Shakespeare / Literature
- Lighting / Mood
- Composition / Aesthetics
- ...

2. The Prompt as a Set of Anchors

The LLM/conditioning creates anchors for the key concepts in the prompt.

- Anchors (from prompt)
- rock
 - academic discourse
 - emergent misalignment (AI)
 - Shakespeare
 - reflection / view / opinion
 - moody lighting
 - symbolic composition

Each anchor pulls the target vector toward its region. The more important a concept, the stronger its pull (weight).

The target vector is the best compromise that satisfies all constraints simultaneously.

High-Dimensional Latent Spaces

(geometric probability space)

3. Guided Diffusion as Constrained Walk

Diffusion starts from pure noise (random point) and iteratively moves toward the target vector while staying in high-probability regions.

At each step, the model:

- denoises
- follows the gradient of high probability
- respects all anchors (guide from LLM)

4. Decoding to Image

The final latent vector is decoded (generative model decoder) into pixels.

Decoding uses learned mappings from latent space to pixel space, producing coherent details, textures, lighting, and composition.

Zooming In: How the Latent Space Works

A. Local Neighborhoods (Manifolds)

Each concept lives on a curved manifold (intrinsic structure) within the high-dimensional space.

B. Combining Distant Concepts

Even if concepts are far apart in straight-line distance, the model finds a path through high-density regions that makes them compatible.

C. Constraint Satisfaction in Latent Space

The target vector sits in a region that balances all constraints. Moving away in any direction would violate at least one.

Forces (Gradients) from Anchors

- ➡ pull from Rock
- ➡ pull from Academic Discourse
- ➡ pull from AI / Misalignment
- ➡ pull from Reflection / Opinion
- ➡ pull from Shakespeare
- ➡ pull from Lighting / Mood
- ➡ pull from Composition

Result: net force = 0 (balanced) → stable target vector

Why This Produces Meaningful Images

- ✓ Concepts are not glued together as separate objects, but blended in a shared representation.
- ✓ The model reasons in terms of relations and compatibility, not just keywords.
- ✓ Diffusion explores, refines, and settles in the most coherent region that satisfies everything.
- ✓ The decoder turns that abstract solution into a concrete image.

Key Takeaway

The latent space is not a simple lookup table. It is a high-dimensional geometry of meaning where concepts, relations, styles, and structures live in proximity if they are compatible.

Unification Mechanism

Anchors + Geometry + Guidance + Diffusion = Coherent Image

Intuition

The model doesn't "paste" concepts together. It finds a single point in a vast space that best expresses all of them at once.

Analogy

Like finding the perfect harmony in music: different notes (concepts) combine into one chord (scene) that sounds right.

FROM PROMPT TO IMAGE: THE TOMATO EXAMPLE

How a text prompt becomes an image

Note: This is a high-level conceptual diagram. Real systems use more complex architectures, multiple encoders, cross-attention, classifier-free guidance, and many optimization tricks.

FROM COMPLEX PROMPT TO COHERENT IMAGE: THE JOINT OPERATION EXAMPLE

How a complex, multi-concept prompt becomes the final image

HOW A RICH, COHERENT IMAGE CAN EMERGE FROM A MINIMAL PROMPT IN A RECURSIVE SESSION

Not just prompt → image. World → interpretation → scene construction → latent guidance → image.

HOW THIS IMAGE STABILIZED: FROM MANY PLAUSIBLE ALTERNATIVES TO ONE COHERENT OUTCOME

At every step, many possibilities exist in latent space. The model iteratively steers, scores, and refines until one solution best satisfies all constraints.

1. INITIAL NOISE
Infinite possibilities

Start: pure random noise in latent space. Every direction represents a possible world.

2. MANY EARLY INTERPRETATIONS
(High diversity, low coherence)

After a few denoising steps, many different scenes fit the minimal prompt. All are plausible. None are fully consistent yet.

3. GUIDANCE BEGINS TO STEER
(Constraints start to apply)

The conditioning package (from the LLM) pushes the process toward regions that satisfy more constraints and away from others.

4. MID-COURSE CONVERGENCE
(Fewer viable regions)

The search space collapses around a few strong candidates that satisfy most constraints.

5. FINAL STABILIZATION
(One coherent solution)

One solution best satisfies all constraints simultaneously. Further refinement adds detail without changing the meaning.

6. WHAT HAPPENS IN LATENT SPACE (THE COMPETITION)

Step 0: Random noise
Step 10: Many directions open
Step 20: Constraints carve out regions
Step 30: Promising regions amplified
Step 40: Weak regions fade away
Step 50: A few strong basins remain
Step 60: One basin dominates
Step N: Final convergence

● Style & mood ● Characters & identities ● Composition & layout ● Lighting & time (night) ● Objects & interactions ● Story & symbolic constraints ● Coherence score (overall fit)

The white path shows the trajectory of the current sample as it moves through latent space, following the gradient of all constraints.

7. WHY THIS SOLUTION WON

- ✓ Correct characters (tomato leader, veggies, Claude, DeepSeek, ChatGPT, robots, train)
- ✓ Joint operation & teamwork clearly shown
- ✓ Mission control / operation context
- ✓ Night scene with cinematic lighting
- ✓ Hopeful mood with emotional depth
- ✓ Pixar-like but detailed
- ✓ Memorial & story continuity
- ✓ Logistics, tools, and action visible
- ✓ No vegetable left behind (theme)

Highest overall coherence score across all constraints.

8. SCORING & SELECTION (At each step)

Each candidate region is scored on multiple dimensions.

The model follows the gradient of the combined score, not any single criterion.

9. PLAUSIBLE ALTERNATIVES THAT LOST OUT (Examples at mid-stage)

<p>Bright Daytime Festival Fun, but wrong time & mood.</p> <p>Why it lost: ✗ No veggies ✗ No organic feel ✗ Wrong theme</p>							
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All of these were valid directions in latent space. The model explored them, scored them, and moved on.

10. REFINEMENT TO DETAIL

Once the best region is found, refinement adds high-frequency detail step by step without changing the core structure.

Texture, small objects, text, micro-lighting, expressions, and fine details are layered in.

THE ROLE OF THE LLM THROUGHOUT

- Recall World State**: Remembers everything from the conversation: characters, events, relationships, symbols, mood, history.
- Infer Intent**: Understands that "final joint-rescue operation" means: culmination, unity, success with cost, hope.
- Plan Scene**: Constructs a rich scene plan with entities, actions, setting, mood, composition priorities.
- Package Constraints**: Encodes this plan as a conditioning package (text embeddings, style embeddings, layout bias, etc.).
- Guide Generation**: Conditions the diffusion process at every step, steering, scoring, and pruning.
- Evaluate & Refine**: Continuously evaluates coherence and refines until the best solution stabilizes.

★ KEY INSIGHT

The image is not "retrieved". It is constructed through a competitive process in latent space, guided by a rich, LLM-built understanding of the world and the story.

Many plausible worlds are explored. One becomes the story you see.

From Prompt to Pineapple: How an Image is Created

FROM STORY CONTEXT TO SUSPICION: HOW THE NEXT SCENE IS IMAGINED AND CREATED

You ask: "Show me why the pineapple starts suspecting Madame Poire."
There is no fixed script—only story context, possibilities, and guidance.

